

Superparamagnetic Heterotermopolymer Developed Using Nanoparticles of Magnetite Complexed by Copaiba Oil-Resin

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Abstract

Magnetite nanoparticles was diluted at different concentration on copaiba oil resin *in natura*, heating until high temperature and quickly freezing until obtaining an heterotermopolymer of copaiba oil (organic glass). $\text{CO}_x\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ samples with $x = 20, 10, 2, 1, 0.5$ and 0 were successfully obtained. X-ray diffraction allied Rietveld refinement confirm cubic structure with $Fd-3m$ space group, and that the values of the network parameters and crystallite size estimated are not affected by the addition of the copaiba oil resin and the sample manufacturing process. XRD and FTIR spectrum confirms that the Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles presence on the organic glass from copaiba resin. TEM image for Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles show homogeneously spherical shape and particles mean sizes estimated in accordance with that obtained from XRD analysis. Magnetization as a function of magnetic field at room temperature renormalized by mass obtained for Fe_3O_4 sample indicate the presence of hysteresis loop with small values coercive field and saturation magnetization at decreases considerably with reduction of concentration Fe_3O_4 in organic glasses, evidencing the diamagnetic behavior of the copaiba oil resin.

Keywords: Copaiba oil, Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, Organic glass, Heterotermopolymer.

1- Introduction

Biomaterials like plant oils have been widely investigated because represent a renewable resource that can be used a variety of biomedical applications due biocompatibility.

This materials maybe synthesized in the laboratory via a variety of chemical approaches including metallic components, polymers, ceramics or composite materials [1]. The organic glasses (OG) derived from oils (castor oil, sunflower, cotton, corn) are being investigated because their composition of oils can be obtain different types polymers, plastics, lubricants, and biopharmaceutical applications.

Copaiba oil resin (CO) for *Copaifera Langsdorfii* species is obtained from these trees found mainly in the Amazon region in Brazil, and for many years CO has been used for a variety of pharmacological purposes, and several medical studies shown anti-inflammatory and healing activities properties [2–4]. CO chemical composition is basically a mixt of sesquiterpenes (hydrocarbons) and diterpenes (carboxylic acids). CO studies have shown that diterpenes are responsible for the medicinal properties found, but present some toxicity in some cells [3,5]. Magnetic nanoparticles have been the subject of intense research to its wide range of technological applications to biomedicine [6–8]. Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles have been intensively investigate because of their properties very interesting like stable against oxidation, bio-compatibility, low toxicity [7,9,10].

The combining of the potential medicinal properties of the CO organic glass and magnetic Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles is unprecedented, and can generate a high range of properties and possible applications, so the synthesis and characterization of this type of material becomes very interesting. In this paper, we produce $\text{CO}_x\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ organic glass at different concentrations: $x = 0.5, 2.0, 10$ and 20 . XRD allied Rietveld refinement and $M_{vs}H$ measurements are reported. The nanoparticles mean sizes and networks was obtained from analysis of XRD diffraction. SEM and TEM images was performed to determinate size and morphology of the samples. FTIR analysis was possible observed types of binding. Finally, magnetization measurements as a function magnetic field at room temperature for study behavior of this organic glass.

2- Experimental Details

In this work, $\text{CO}_x\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ ($x = 20, 10, 0.5$ and 0.1) organic glass was obtained by dilution and burning of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles and pure copaiba oil. Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles were synthesized by co-precipitation [13]. Copaiba oil resin was collected from *Copaifera* tree (*Copaifera Langsdorffii* Desf.) in forest region of the Rondônia State, Brazil. In the process of preparation of the samples 40 ml of oil of copaiba in nature was taken with a

$x\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ concentration (x) of the nanoparticles from the initial mass of the oil. The nanoparticles were diluted in CO with aid of a tip ultrasound apparatus and then this mixture was heated for 3 hours, with abrupt cooling in the solution every 30 minutes [19]. The final organic glass obtained was macerated and then the powders were obtained for measurements of drifting and magnetization. Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) were performed in DTG-60H Instrument of the Shimadzu. The measurements were collected in argon flow from 20 to 600 °C at 10° C/min. X-ray diffraction measurements in room temperature were collected using a Shimadzu X-ray diffractometer with a Cu-K α source in the continuous mode with steep 0.5°/min taking range 15-80°. Rietveld refinement was carried out for using the DBWS 9807 code approach as implement in the DBWSTools2.3 program [11,12]. The full width at half-maximum (FWHM) of the more intense peaks obtained from Rietveld refinement were used to calculate the average crystallite size through Scherrer equation, after correction for instrumental peaks broadening with LaB6 standard sample. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was performed using either a spectrometer Varian 660. The samples were analyzed in transmission mode at room temperature and spectra were collected from 4000 to 430 cm⁻¹. TGA, XRD and FTIR analysis was performed in Laboratory of Analytics Technical (LAMUTA) of the Federal University of Mato Grosso – UFMT. Sizes and morphologies of the nanoparticles were obtained using transmission electron microscopy (JEM-2100) and Scanning Electron Microscope (JSM-6610) at the High Resolution Microscopy Multiuser Laboratory (LabMic) of the University of Goiania - UFG. Brazil. Magnetization as a function at filed at room temperature was performed in Vibrant sample Magnetometer of the Federal University of Goiania - UFG. Brazil.

3-Results and Discussions

TGA curves for Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles, organic glass from CO resin oil and CO_{+x}Fe₃O₄ (x = 0.5, 2.0, 10 and 20%) samples are shown in Figure 1. TGA measurements show that they are dominated by thermal decomposition of Copaiba oil resin, with the addition of Fe₃O₄ visibly affecting the loss of mass compared to pure CO. All samples undergo degradation at 40 °C, but the Fe³O₄ nanoparticles show higher thermal resistance. For Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles, a loss of 9% mass up to 500 °C has been observed, which remains constant up to 1000 °C (data not shown here). This may be

due to loss of remaining water and agents. For organic glass containing only CO, marked loss in thermogram was observed between 200 and 420 ° C due to the component sesquiterpenes still present in the sample. Other sesquiterpenes contribute with a slow mass loss process between 420 and 570 ° C, occurring the total mass loss practically above 570 ° C [13]. Above 600 ° C, the amount of mass remains constant by weight, and this suggests that the nanoparticles were vitrified with diterpene acids and the iron nanoparticles did not degrade. A final mass variation of the proportional was observed the amount of nanoparticles diluted in the oil.

Figure 1: TGA curve for the CO resin, Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles and CO + xFe₃O₄ (x = 0.5, 2.0, 10 and 20 %).

Figure 2 shows the XRD measurements for CO + xFe₃O₄ (x = 0.5, 2.0, 10 and 20 %) powder samples taken at room temperature. The red curves represent the calculated pattern from the model structure used in the Rietveld refinement to fit the experimental data. The blue line in the bottom of each measurement means the difference between experimental and calculated data. The Rietveld analyses of XRD patterns indicate that single-phase Fe₃O₄ was observed above 2 % concentration and the samples shows a cubic structure with the *Fd-3m* space group.

Figure 2: Calculated (I_{calc}) experimental (I_{exp}) XRD patterns for pure copaiba oil, Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles and $\text{CO} + x\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ samples collected at room temperature. The vertical bars correspond to the peaks positions of literature pattern for the Fe_3O_4 (ICSD 86177).

Table I presents the lattices parameters a , volume (Vol.), size mean and goodness of fit factor (χ^2) for Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles and $\text{CO}_x\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ samples taken from the left file Rietveld refinement. The data show that good adjustments were obtained and that the values of the network parameters and crystallite size estimated are not affected by the addition of the copaiba oil and the sample manufacturing process. For the samples produced with concentrations of less than 10 % it was not possible to observe diffraction peaks due to the higher amount of oil in the sample and organic glass copaiba oil is amorphous.

Table I: Size and structural parameters obtained from Rietveld refinement.

Sample	a (Å)	Vol. (Å ³)	Size (nm)	χ^2
Fe_3O_4	8.3893 (2)	590.45 (2)	26.7 (1)	1.15
$x = 20$	8.4140 (3)	595.67 (3)	33.4 (2)	1.20
$x = 10$	8.3989 (3)	592.48 (4)	31.8 (3)	1.10

Figure 3 shows TEM and SEM images for Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles (a) and copaiba oil resin (b). TEM image for Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles show homogeneously spherical shape the in inset of Figure 3 (a) show the particles size histogram obtained from different regions of the samples and fitted by log-normal distributions. It is worth to say that the

particles mean sizes estimated from TEM are in accordance with that obtained from XRD analysis. The SEM image for CO without addition Fe_3O_4 show a irregular surface. Optic microscopy images (Figure 4) is possible observe the increase concentration Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles in organic glass.

Figure 3: (a) TEM image for Fe_3O_4 and (b) MEV image for CO. In inset of (a) image, we show the particles size histograms obtained from different regions of the sample and fitted by log-normal distribution.

Figure 4: Microscopy optic images for $\text{CO} + x\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ ($x = 0.5, 2.0, 10$ and 20%) organic glass.

Fourier transform infrared spectrum (FTIR) of the pure copaiba oil, Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles and $\text{CO}_x\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ samples are shown in Figure 4. The first spectrum matches well to published spectra characteristic with components of sesquiterpenes and diterpene acids that make up most of the polymer chain present CO resin [14,15]. The strongest absorptions are the wide range of aliphatic hydrocarbons (CH) near 2900 cm^{-1}

and the stretching of carboxyls (CO_2H) by about 1700 cm^{-1} . The position and intensity of the fingerprint bands, including the carboxylic acid (C-O) bands at approximately 1400 and 1300 to 1200 cm^{-1} and the carbon-carbon flexion modes of the alkenes between 730 and 7475 cm^{-1} . For the Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, the FTIR spectrum shows the main bands near 3440 , 1650 and 580 cm^{-1} assigned to O-H stretching, O-H bending, and Fe-O stretching, respectively [16]. In comparison with the CO and Fe_3O_4 spectra was observed that for the $\text{CO}_x\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ samples they present a combination of these two spectra, in addition to new absorption peaks. These new absorption peaks around 1600 cm^{-1} are peaks characteristic of the COO-Fe bond, which may be related to the reaction of hydroxyl radical groups on the Fe_3O_4 surface with carboxylate groups of the copaiba resin [17]. Both the peak at 598 cm^{-1} and 3458 cm^{-1} confirm the existence of Fe-O binding. Obviously, the characteristic absorption peaks of -OH at 3400 cm^{-1} decreased, indicating that the components of the copaiba resin may be grafted onto the surface of Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles [18].

Figure 4: FTIR spectra for pure copaiba oil, Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles and $\text{CO}_x\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ samples.

Figure 5 displays magnetization as a function of magnetic field (M vs H) at $T = 300\text{ K}$ for Fe_3O_4 , and $\text{CO}_x\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ with $x = 20, 10, 2, 1, 0.5$ and 0 organic glasses renormalized by mass. M vs H curves for $x = 2, 0.5$ and 0 samples diluted reveals a

diamagnetic behavior is stronger and prevails. The magnetization at 20 kOe applied magnetic field of sample Fe_3O_4 , CO, $x = 20$, $x=10$, $x=2$ and $x = 0.5$ are 51 emu/g, 18 emu/g, 0,06 emu/g, 0,015 emu/g and -0,018 emu/g, respectively. For Fe_3O_4 sample was observed the presence of hysteresis loop with small values coercive field decreases considerably with reduction of concentration Fe_3O_4 in samples. For bulk maghemite, a magnetization saturation of 90 emu/g at 5 K is theoretically expected [18]. The reduction of magnetization in magnetic nanoparticles can be a surface phenomenon, being intensified by dilution in copaiba resin oil. At the surface of magnetic nanomaterials, the spins are not so well ordered as in the interior, as than surface to volume ratio of nanoparticles is larger by a few orders of magnitude than that of bulk materials, the contribution of spin disorder at the surface to the magnetization is relevant, causing significant reduction in the magnetization saturation.

Figure 5: Magnetization as a function of magnetic field at room temperature patterns for pure copaiba oil, Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles and $\text{CO} + x\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ organic glasses.

4- Conclusions

Organic glass from CO oil with nanoparticles Fe_3O_4 diluted in different concentration were successfully obtained. X-ray diffraction allied Rietveld refinement and magnetic measurements as function of magnetic field were used to characterize the samples. XRD

patterns confirm cubic structure with $Fd-3m$ space group. From results of XRD and TEM the mean size of nanoparticles is less 30 nm. The dilution in CO resin not caused change in size mean in Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles and affect considerably the magnetic properties at room temperature.

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